

EFFECT OF UNINTENDED HYPOTHERMIA ON SURGICAL SITE INFECTION IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING ORTHOPEDIC SURGERY

Keywords

Hypothermia,

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Büşra Badak¹, Kübra Yılmaz²

ABSTRACT

Patients undergoing orthopedic surgery are at risk for perioperative hypothermia, which depends on the degree and duration of the surgery. Perioperative hypothermia can affect many systems due to decreased blood flow and cellular functions. One of these systems is the immune system, and hypothermia may lead to surgical site infections. The aim of this study is to determine the effects of unintended hypothermia on the formation of surgical site infections in patients who have undergone orthopedic surgery and to highlight the roles, responsibilities, and duties of surgical nurses in preventing hypothermia. To determine the effect of perioperative hypothermia on surgical site infections, 318 articles were screened from various databases, and 9 articles that met the specified inclusion criteria were analyzed. The study was conducted following the PRISMA protocol using a systematic review method. In 77.7% of the 9 articles reviewed, a significant relationship was found between surgical site infections and hypothermia. It has been determined that hypothermia developing during the perioperative period is effective in the development of surgical site infections. This situation underscores the importance of the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of surgical nurses regarding perioperative temperature management. Preventing hypothermia is a crucial step in positively influencing patients' recovery processes and reducing infection risk. Furthermore, maintaining normothermia during the perioperative process is thought to be effective in reducing infection rates.

INTRODUCTION

Unwanted perioperative hypothermia is defined as a drop in body temperature below 36°C, occurring from 1 hour prior to anesthesia and lasting up to 24 hours after the surgical process.¹ Various factors contribute to the occurrence of unwanted hypothermia, including patient-related factors such as age, American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) score, the presence of chronic illnesses, trauma and burns, and smoking, as well as risk factors related to the surgical procedure itself, including anesthetic gases, intravenous fluids, type of anesthesia, premedication with sedatives and opioids, and operating room temperature.² As surgical duration increases, there is a decrease in heat production and an increase in heat loss, which particularly raises the risk of unwanted hypothermia in major and moderate surgeries.³ Literature indicates that the incidence of hypothermia in surgical patients ranges from 50% to 70%.^{4,5,6} In orthopedic cases, Dong (2022) reported an incidence of 7.3% in upper extremity fractures, Hu et al. (2020) reported 18.6% in open fracture surgeries, Marusic et al. (2021) reported 5.4% in total joint arthroplasties, Magalhaes et al. (2024) reported an incidence of 0.5-6.5% in patients undergoing foot and ankle surgeries, and Jildeh et al. (2018) reported varying incidences between 37.5% and 68.9% in shoulder arthroplasties.^{7,8,9,10}

Patients experiencing unwanted hypothermia are at higher risk for increased discomfort, shivering, and prolonged hospital stays.¹¹ Unwanted hypothermia affects multiple systems in different ways. In the cardiovascular system, it can reduce cardiac output, leading to arrhythmias, hypertension, and consequently myocardial ischemia. In the respiratory system, hypothermia increases the

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1-Gazi University Hospital, Ankara, Türkiye, busrabadak@icloud.com, ORCID: 0009-0007-9321-2385

2*-Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University, Ankara, Türkiye, kubrayilmaz@aybu.edu.tr, ORCID: 0000-0003-1334-6353

oxygen demand, leading to hypoxia, lactic acid accumulation, bradypnea, and acid-base imbalances. In the hematopoietic system, it alters enzymatic reactions and affects platelet function, increasing the need for bleeding and transfusion. In the gastrointestinal system, it can lead to ileus and pancreatitis.^{12, 13} Additionally, in the immune system, hypothermia impairs systemic functions due to decreased blood flow to immune organs, and hypoxia at the surgical site increases the risk of surgical site infections due to inadequate oxygenation of the tissue.¹⁴ Surgical site infections are among the most reported infections in healthcare, accounting for approximately one-fifth of all reported infections and leading to significant morbidity and mortality.¹⁵ Surgical site infections are defined as infections that occur as a result of a surgical intervention or within 30 to 90 days following the intervention.¹⁶

Guidelines for preventing unwanted hypothermia emphasize the importance of measuring body temperature in designated areas, conducting regular assessments from the same site, selecting appropriate methods for preventing hypothermia (both active and passive warming) prior to surgery, and utilizing combinations of these methods as well as pre-heating before the intraoperative period.¹⁷ The Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) Society's consensus guidelines on perioperative care for lumbar spinal fusion and total hip-knee prosthesis recommend active warming of the patient and maintaining normothermia throughout the perioperative process.¹⁸ The literature corroborates these findings. Kang et al. (2020) initiated active warming in patients undergoing upper extremity surgery at temperatures of 40-43 °C in the waiting room and applied a combination of warming methods (such as head wraps, compression stockings, warming blankets, forced-air warming devices, and warmed intravenous fluids) during the intraoperative period. Results indicated that in the control group, body temperature dropped below 36 °C within 45 minutes after the start of surgery, while significantly better thermal comfort and satisfaction levels were recorded in the intervention group.¹⁹ Since heat loss is most pronounced from the head and feet during surgery, keeping the patient warm through to the postoperative period is advised. Oh et al. (2023) conducted a randomized controlled trial with patients undergoing liver transplantation from living donors and found that pre-warming decreased intraoperative hypothermia by 85%.²⁰ Cho et al. (2024) divided patients undergoing

transurethral bladder or prostate resection into two groups; patients in the pre-warmed group received 10 minutes of active warming with forced-air warming devices and warmed intravenous fluids, while the control group received no warming and was given room temperature intravenous fluids. The study concluded that pre-warming effectively prevented intraoperative hypothermia and managed thermal comfort better in the post-anesthesia care unit.²¹ Lee et al. (2020) observed that among 26 patients who did not receive pre-warming, 8 experienced shivering, while only 1 out of 25 patients in the pre-warmed group did, underscoring the effectiveness of pre-warming in preventing hypothermia.²² The literature suggests that a minimum pre-warming duration of 30 minutes is beneficial, with at least 10 minutes recommended to prevent the side effects and complications associated with hypothermia. Overall, it is critical to enhance awareness and implement proper perioperative temperature management strategies to reduce the incidence of unwanted hypothermia, thus improving surgical outcomes and patient recovery.²³

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted using the systematic review methodology in accordance with the PRISMA protocol guidelines. Our research involved a comprehensive search of databases employing Turkish keywords "ortopedi, ortopedik cerrahi, hipotermi, cerrahi alan enfeksiyonu, normotermi" and English keywords "orthopedics, orthopedic surgery, hypothermia, surgical wound infection," focusing on publications from January 2019 to January 2024. A total of 9 articles that met the inclusion criteria were reviewed. Letters to the editor, reviews, systematic reviews, and case reports were excluded. The study included experimental, cohort, prospective, retrospective observational, cross-sectional, and descriptive studies published in Turkish or English with accessible full-text.

RESULTS

A total of 10 articles were screened from the PubMed database, 282 from Google Scholar, 20 from the Ulakbim Turkish Medical Database, 0 from Turkish Medline, and 6 from Scopus; ultimately, 9 articles were included based on meeting the inclusion criteria. Among the reviewed studies, 44.4% (n=4) were prospective, 44.4% (n=4) were retrospective, and 11.1% (n=1) were randomized studies.

Table 1-Studies indicating the effect of prewarming on surgical site infection

Author/ Year	Sample /Applied surgery	Study Type	Warming type	Warming time / measurement type	Metod	Result
Buraimoh et al. ; 2019	74 patients lumbar spine surgery.	Prospective randomized controlled trial	Bair Hugger	Not determined. / foley catheter	Active heating devices have been used to warm the upper and lower extremities during the intraoperative period, with patients divided into group 1 (upper extremity) and group 2 (lower extremity). Body temperature measurements were taken at 15-minute intervals.	In Group 1, surgical site infections (either superficial or deep) were identified in 5 patients. No infections were observed in Group 2. Despite successful temperature management, the study results indicate a problematic relationship between mild intraoperative hypothermia and postoperative outcomes..
Chataule et al. ; 2020	100 patients who underwent femur fracture surgery	Single-blind, prospective randomized controlled trial	forced air blanket	30 minutes / Infrared tympanic membrane thermometer	Patients were divided into two groups: Group A, which received active warming for 30 minutes prior to surgery, and Group B, which did not receive active warming. Body temperature was measured every 10 minutes during the intraoperative period and every 15 minutes in the postoperative recovery room.	In patients in Group A (who received active warming), the risk of shivering and surgical site infection was found to be lower.
Kümin et al. ; 2021	257 Hemiarthroplasty surgery	Randomized pilot study	Forced air and resistant fabric	Not determined/ Zero flow thermometer	Forced air and resistance fabric heating units have divided patients into 2 groups. Body temperatures were measured with a constant zero flow thermometer.	It has been determined that preventing the development of involuntary hypothermia is a correct and effective way to prevent surgical infections that may occur post-operatively, and that the resistance heating system (RHW) is effective in preven-
Charles-Lozoya et al.; 2021	300 Patients undergoing hip fracture surgery	Prospective survival study	No active prewarming applied.	Rectal measurement with Omron MC-343F. Tokyo, Japan digital thermometer	In a 30-day period, 300 patients were monitored postoperatively to determine whether hypothermia increased the mortality risk.	25% of the patients were recorded as hypothermic. It was found that patients who were hypothermic during the surgical process had a higher risk of surgical site infection and mortality. Additionally, a high incidence of hypothermia was recorded in patients who received blood transfusions.
Williams et al.; 2018	929 Patients undergoing hip fracture surgery	Single-center retrospective study	Not determined.	Tympani thermometer	929 patients have been analyzed. The number of normothermic patients was found to be 837, while the number of hypothermic patients was 92.	The overall incidence of unwanted hypothermia in patients who underwent hip fracture surgery was determined to be 10%. With the ratio of hypothermic patients to normothermic patients being found to be 1.9 times higher, the 30-day mortality rate was observed to be higher. It was found that there was a higher rate of hospital readmission due to postoperative respiratory infections and wound contamination.

Table 1-Studies indicating the effect of prewarming on surgical site infection (Continue)

Kim et al. ; 2023	3945 Patients undergoing unilateral hip hemiarthro- plasty and total hip ar- throplasty surgery	Retrospective mass study	Forced warming devices and conduction devices	air de- vices and	Not deter- mined.			Patients were investigated in 2 groups as those who underwent intraoperative heating device application and those who did not receive intraopera- tive heating device application. I	In patients who did not receive intraope- rative heating, the risk of surgical site infection was found to be 1.9 times higher. In male groups where no heating device was used during surgery, the risk of wound infection was recorded to be 2.8 times higher. When active heating device was not applied, the risk of in- fection significantly increased in males, patients under 70 years old, and patients undergoing total hip arthroplasty.
Hu et al. ; 2020	2692 Patients who under- went open fracture sur- gery	Retrospective multicenter study	Not deter- mined.		Not deter- mined.			Body temperature, duration of surgery, type of fracture, and duration of anesthesia are factors that have been studied to affect the forma- tion of surgical site infections	The incidence of surgical site infections in open fracture operations is generally 18.6, while the rates for superficial and deep infections are reported as 17.0% and 1.6%, respectively. A total of 501 patients have been diagnosed with sur- gical site infections. In particular, the washing solutions used during open fracture debridement cause a decrease in body temperature. The prolonged dura- tion of surgery and anesthesia also lead to a decrease in body temperature, and among the risk factors, intraoperative hypothermia (accepted body temperatu- re value in the study <36.4) has been identified as a factor contributing to the development of surgical site infections.
Tombak, ; 2019	140 Lower extremity surgery	Prospective, randomized, single-blind study	Not deter- mined.		Not deter- mined.			Patients divided into two groups in the form of a study and control group; those in the study group were actively heated with a Bair hugger. The control group was covered with a blanket, which is a passive heating method that is routinely applied.	No significant difference was found in terms of surgical site infection between patients heated with special heating methods and those heated with a normal blanket. However, on postoperative day 0, no hypothermia was observed in the study group. While the body temperatu- re of the intervention group using the special heating method was maintained within normal limits (36.47 C), the body temperature of patients in the control group was recorded as hypothermic (35.78 C).
Yamada et al.; 2020	8841 Patients undergoing orthopedic surgery	Retrospective observational study	Not deter- mined.		Not deter- mined.	Rectal or bladder meas- urement		Orthopedic surgi- cal operations were compared for normothermic and hypothermic pati- ents regarding the rates of surgical site infection, urinary tract infec- tion, respiratory tract infection, and mortality over a period of 30 days.	11.4% of the patients (n=1008) were recorded as hypothermic. In hypother- mic patients, surgical site infections (n=8), urinary tract infections (n=14), respiratory tract infections (n=9), and hospital-acquired infections (n=37) were identified. The association of surgical site infections with normother- mic patients has not found to be signifi- cant; however, the incidence of morbidi- ty was found to be higher in hypother- mic patients.

When examining the research sample, 44.4% (n=4) consisted of patients undergoing fracture surgery, 22.2% (n=2) underwent arthroplasty, while the remaining 33.4% (n=3) comprised patients with general orthopedic conditions and those experiencing hypothermia. Upon analysis of the results, 77.7% (n=7) of the studies found a significant relationship between surgical site infection (SSI) and hypothermia (Table 1).

CONCLUSION

Preventing surgical site infections is one of the vital responsibilities of nurses, and the prevention of SSIs is considered an indicator of the quality of care. Utilizing evidence-based practices and ensuring healthcare professionals are knowledgeable about risk factors is essential for SSI prevention. One of the risk factors contributing to SSIs is hypothermia. Despite the variability in sample sizes and orthopedic surgery groups across the studies included in our research, they collectively indicate the influence of perioperative hypothermia on the incidence of surgical site infections (Table 1). Current guidelines emphasize maintaining normothermia as a critical measure in preventing SSIs. Recommendations from organizations such as TARD, ASPAN, and AST advocate for employing active warming methods such as forced-air heating, heated water mattresses, and passive warming techniques during patient transport and throughout the perioperative process to maintain body temperature. Furthermore, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (2017) recommends implementing active warming during the intraoperative period. ERAS guidelines also underscore the importance of maintaining patient normothermia throughout the entirety of the surgical process. A review of the literature indicates that unintended hypothermia may lead to surgical site infections. Maintaining normothermia is therefore crucial in preventing these infections. In preventing unintended hypothermia, surgical nurses have a significant role within the team; they should regularly monitor body temperature throughout the perioperative period and implement active (forced-air warming, warming intravenous fluids, heating anesthetic gases) and passive methods (blankets, socks, surgical drapes, quilts, sheets) to mitigate heat loss caused by radiation and evaporation, thereby potentially reducing the incidence of SSIs.^{33, 34, 35}

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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No

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